

TEACHING WRITING ASPECTS TO INTERMEDIATE LEVEL STUDENTS

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Abstract: By analyzing the shortcomings of the traditional approach and the drawbacks of the modern approach, the author attempts to explore a better way for the teaching of intermediate-level writing skills to EFL students. Taking into account all of the factors which are involved in good writing, the author puts forward a balanced approach to such teaching and provides some principles and techniques for the classroom procedures in which the balanced approach is applied

Keywords: Traditional approach, Modern approach, A balanced approach
Process approach: Moves away from a concentration on the written product to an emphasis on the process of writing.

1. Introduction Since the theory of "communicative competence" was advanced by Hymes, it has to a great extent encouraged and enlightened many linguists who are not satisfied with the analysis of language merely based on its structures and forms. So communicative teaching approach gradually came into being. Nowadays, it has been generally admitted that the communicative teaching approach has some merits in the improvement of learners' communicative competence. As one aspect of the communicative competence, the ability of writing can also be greatly improved through this approach. However, the communicative approach is not the cure-all, and it also has some defects of its own. So in the practice of the teaching of writing skills to EFL students, we'd better seek an approach which comprises the advantages of both the traditional and the modern teaching approaches. In the following passage, we will try to explore such an approach based on the analysis of the traditional and the modern approaches to the teaching of intermediate-level writing skills to EFL students.

2. The traditional approach The most influential approach of the traditional methods of organizing language teaching is that of the 3Ps: presentation, practice, and production. The first stage is generally focused on a single point of grammar which is presented explicitly or implicitly to maximize the chances that the underlying rule will be understood and internalized. This would essentially aim at the development of declarative knowledge. This initial stage would be

followed by practice activities, designed to automatize the newly grasped rule, and to convert declarative to procedural knowledge. And at the production stage the degree of control and support would be reduced, and the learner would be required to produce language more spontaneously, based on meanings the learner himself or herself would want to express. Reflected in the teaching of writing at the inter-mediate level in foreign-language classrooms, such an approach often appears as the teaching of basic sentence-level writing skills, with organizational skills added. In basic writing training, often a student is given an example sentence whose meaning is explained; then the grammar pattern is taught; finally, the student is asked to write similar sentences using different content. At the intermediate level, the student is given an example paragraph to read; the overall organizational pattern of the paragraph is explicated; finally, the student is told to write a similar paragraph about a different subject. For example, students might be given a paragraph to read in which two people are compared in terms of physical characteristics. Then the teacher will demonstrate the patterns for comparing the attributes or characteristics of things at the sentence level, and the overall organizational pattern of a paragraph of comparison, followed by exercises for practice. Finally, the students might be asked to write a paragraph of their own comparing two of their friends in terms of physical characteristics. This is the traditional "read-analyze-write" approach. Practitioners of the modern approach to writing point out that the traditional approach is deficient in two important respects. First, they teacher views the student's writing as a product. She assumes that the student knows how to write and uses what the student produces as a test of that ability. Second, the teacher focuses on form, i. e., syntax, grammar, mechanics, and organization, rather than on content. The content is seen mainly as a vehicle for the correct expression of the grammatical and organizational patterns taught, and the correct choice of vocabulary

Product approach: An approach which focuses on producing different kinds of written products and which emphasizes imitation of different kinds of model paragraphs or essays (also called prose model approach).

Strategy: Procedures used in learning, thinking, etc. which serve as a way of reaching a goal. **The Controlled-to-Free Approach:** Learners work on given material and perform strictly prescribed operations on it. The approach emphasizes accuracy rather than fluency or originality. **The Free-Writing Approach:** Stresses quantity of writing rather than quality. The emphasis is that

intermediate-level students should put content and fluency first and not worry about form.

The Paragraph-Pattern Approach: Instead of accuracy of grammar or fluency of content, it stresses organization (copying, analyzing the form and imitating model paragraphs, putting scrambled sentences into paragraph order).
The Communicative Approach: Stresses the purpose of a piece of writing and the audience for it, extending the readership. Interaction through the written message is the goal: what is written should be a purposeful communication on the practical or imaginative level, expressed in such a way that it is comprehensible to another person.
The Grammar-Syntax Organization Approach: Links the purpose of a piece of writing to the forms that are needed to convey the message.

Reports proposed on the theme: Different approaches to teaching writing. Peculiarities of writing as the means of communication. Cooperative techniques in teaching writing. Process-oriented approach to teaching writing.

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